

Floristic Diversity of Patiala district, Punjab, India

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Abstract: *The current work is collating description of floristic diversity in district Patiala. Six different blocks of district Patiala were discernible through cluster analysis. Survey was carried out under the scheme of People's Biodiversity Register sponsored by National Biodiversity Authority, Government of India. Total 362 species of plants were identified which belongs to 87 families. 11% shrubs, 10% were climbers, 24% tree, 55% herbs species in this area. 158 of cultivated plant species were found out of which 223 were purely wild species and 19 are wild cum cultivated. Our work primarily focuses on the awareness among the locals and documentation of the plant species data. Investigations during this survey indicate that District Patiala is rich in the floristic diversity. Out of total 362 species, 223 purely wild species, 158 plant species were cultivated, and 19 wild cum cultivated was found.*

Keywords: Angiosperm, Documentation, People's Biodiversity Register, National Biodiversity Authority.

1.0 Introduction

India harbour over 2991 species of flowering plants out of with 49 endemic genera belongs to 22 families and 80 taxas [3],[5]. Studied area is located

under the semi-arid and sub-tropical zone of India. Earlier work on documentation of flora of Punjab has been done by [1] [2], [4], [6], [10], [11], [12], [14] [15], [16]. Punjab is blessed

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with 1843 species of Angiosperms belonging to 940 genera and 165 families [14]. The documentation of vegetation composition is one of the first steps toward the formulation of conservation and management strategies, so the present study is an endeavour to investigate the floral diversity so, that conservation should be initiated. We specially emphasized on awareness within the locals regarding the importance of biodiversity simultaneously, execution of People biodiversity registers an action plan of National Biodiversity Authority, India in district Patiala. Our major goal under this study is to involve the local communities for accessing the biodiversity data and to get the traditional knowledge from the locals as well as economic importance of these plants. The present study is carried out to get the comprehensive information of the floral diversity of the district Patiala and including awareness among the villagers toward the conservation of local native species.

2.0 Study area

Geographically district Patiala is located in between 29°49'- 30°40' North latitudes and 75°58'- 76°48' longitudes East with 3218 sq.km geographical area having tropical, semi-arid, hot and subtropical monsoon climatic

conditions and experience five seasons i.e. Summer, Rainy, Autumn, Winter and Spring [9]. Study area has moderately dense forest and divided into six blocks such as (Patiala, Nabha, Ghanaur, Rajpura, Sunam and Patran) which also includes eight protected areas locally called Birs (Kharabgarh, Miranpur & Ghogpur, Kule Majra, Majal, Sanaur, Bahadurgarh and Mallehwal) and five sanctuaries (Bhuner Heri, Moti Bhag, Mehas, Dosanj and Bhadson)

Figure 2.0: Location map of the study area showing Map of District Patiala

3.0 Material and Methods

Study was carried out from September 2019 to September 2021 for the tenure of two years. The preparation of People's Biodiversity Registers (PBRs) involved the active support and cooperation of large number of people including village BMC members, subject experts, farmers, knowledge holder individuals, etc. who were motivated to share their

common as well as specialized knowledge. For the present survey, the standard methodology given by National Biodiversity Authority (NBA) has been adopted. The first step of PBR preparation was to organize preliminary meetings with BMC members and village residents to explain the objectives and purpose of this study. In the second meeting, Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) activity was organized with the help of BMC members, in which panchayat members, BMC members, students, knowledgeable individuals and all those interested in the effort were gathered in common places of the village such as school, Gurudwara sahib, community hall, panchayat hall, etc. During PRA activity, all formats of PBR including crop plants, weeds, ornamental plants, timber yielding plants, fruit plants, medicinal plants, aquatic plants and wild plants were used for discussion with locals [7]. To enlist plant species of the study area, 4 field surveys per season has been conducted for the primary data collection throughout the study area.

During field survey, botanical name of plants, local name, habit, habitat, other important field characters, uses, etc. were recorded in the field notebook. The intensive field surveys on foot were

carried out in different locations of district Patiala in different seasons to collect maximum plants species. Photographic records of flowers, leaves, fruits and barks have been done with the aid of mobile and DSLR camera for documenting evidences of plants. For identification of plants local and regional floras were used [8], [11], [14], [15] and some online tools such as [17] [18] [19] [20] was consulted. The inventory was prepared in accordance with Bentham and Hooker system of classification using currently accepted name by using plants of world online, Royal Botanical Garden, Kew.

4.0 Results and Discussions

Authors believe that district level compilations of regional flora to ensure the updating of the records and also helpful in understanding the impact of temporal changes and change in land use pattern, climate change on the species diversity specifically on plants which will ultimately lead to design and amend the conservation strategies within time. The present investigation has been carried out from September 2019 to September 2021 and a total number of 362 species of angiosperms belongs to 276 genera and 87 families which is 19.15% of totals species of Punjab were recorded. Herbs (55%) dominated the area followed by trees

(24%), shrubs (11%), climbers (10%) species (Figure 4.1). Out of total 362 species, 223 purely wild species, 158 plant species were cultivated, and 19 wild cum cultivated was found. Total 87 Families were recorded out of which Poaceae dominate over other with 36 species of plants followed by Fabaceae (35 species), Asteraceae (24 species), Cucurbitaceae (15 species), Malvaceae (13 species), Euphorbiaceae (13 species), Convolvulaceae, Moraceae (11 species each) (Figure 4.2). The favorable genera which have maximum number of species includes *Ficus* (7), *Ipomoea* (6), *Euphorbia* (5), *Brassica* (5) and *Solanum* (4) species each

Figure 4.1: Graph showing Percentage of species in different plant groups

Figure 4.2: Graph showing dominant families in the region

4.1 Vegetation of aquatic and marshy places

Eichhornia crassipes, *Hydrilla verticillata*, *Ipomoea aquatic*, *Lemna minor*, *Nelumbo nucifera*, *Nymphaea nouchali*, *Nymphaea stellata*, *Typha angustifolia*, *Typha domingensis* and *Spirodela polyrhiza* are main aquatic species growing in the study area. *Eichhornia crassipes* commonly known as Water Hyacinth cover the most of water bodies in area. *Polygonum plebeium*, *Rumex dentatus*, *Ranunculus muricatus*, *Ranunculus reptabundus*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Cyperus difformis*, *Cyperus compressus*, *Cyperus alatus subsp. Albus* found near the marshy places.

4.2 Vegetation of Agriculture fields

Punjab is an agriculture state where two main types of crops i.e. Rabi and Kharif were grown throughout the state. *Triticum aestivum*, *Hordeum vulgare*,

Brassica sp., *Pisum sativum* are main rabi crops whereas *Oryza sativa*, *Pennisetum typhoides*, *Physalis angulata*, *Zea mays* etc. are main Kharif crops. *Luffa acutangula*, *Citrullus colocynthis*, *Cucumis melo*, *Cucurbita pepo*, *Abelmoschus esculentus*, *Solanum melongena*, *Solanum tuberosum*, *Lycopersicon esculentum*, *Momordica charantia* etc are summer grown vegetables whereas *Allium cepa*, *Allium sativum*, *Lathyrus oleraceus*, *Lablab purpureus*, *Daucus carota*, *Brassica rapa*, *Raphanus sativus*, *Spinacia oleracea*, *Curcuma longa* etc are winter grown vegetables in the region. In addition to *Dalbergia sissoo*, *Tectona grandis*, *Melia azedarach*, *Eucalyptus* species are grown as along with the crops in the study area for commercial purpose.

4.3 Fruits grown in area

Mangifera indica, *Psidium guajava*, *Litchi chinensis*, *Citrus species*, *Prunus persica*, *Syzygium cumini*, *Zizyphus jujuba*, *Vitis vinifera*, *Musa paradisiaca* are grown fruit species in kitchen garden and farm houses.

4.4 Avenue plantation

Delonix regia, *Polyalthia longifolia*, *Chukrasia tabularis*, *Toona ciliata*, *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*, *Moringa oleifera*, *Cassia fistula*, *Albizia lebbek*, *Albizia*

procera, *Erythrina variegata*, *Butea monosperma*, *Pongamia pinnata*, *Bauhinia variegata*, *Lagerstroemia speciosa*, *Lagerstroemia indica*, *Ptilostigma malabaricum*, *Putranjivam roxburghii*, *Gladiolus dalenii*, *Jasminum grandiflorum*, *Jasminum sambac*, *Catharanthus roseus*, *Nerium oleander*, *Tabernaemontana divaricate* etc. are trees and shrubs which are grown along road sides, gardens, government organisations, hospitals for ornamental purpose.

4.5 Rare species

Oxystelma esculentum, *Pergularia daemia* and *Bacopa monnieri* are reported at one or two site during survey of the district therefore placed under the rare category.

Figure 4.3: Interacting with local people of Village Chamaru, Ghanour division, Patiala

Major purpose of these survey are the awareness in the locals as conservation without the involvement of native people is not possible so, on every visit

a small gathering for interaction was carried out with the villager is generate, Sarpanch and other members of the Panchayat (Figure 4.3). Interactions emphasized on the conservation of the native plant species, understanding the policies and rules of government. Briefing to the local community's regulation that how to of access to biodiversity resources leading to sustainable harvests and development. Promoting knowledge-based sustainable management of agriculture, forests and

public health so as to enhance the quality of life of the community members. Conserving valued resources, value addition to biodiversity resources and recording of biodiversity related knowledge is the mandate of preparation of People's Biodiversity Register. The list was prepared in accordance with Bentham and Hooker system of classification using currently accepted name in accordance with Plants of World Online, Royal Botanical Garden, Kew (Table 4.1).

Table4.1: List of Plant species reported in Patiala District

Sr. No.	Family	Scientific name	Habit	Source
1	Ranunculaceae	<i>Ranunculus muricatus L.</i>	Herb	Wild
2		<i>Ranunculus reptabundus Rupr.</i>	Herb	Wild
3	Magnoliaceae	<i>Magnolia grandiflora L.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
4	Annonaceae	<i>Monoon longifolium (Sonn.) B.Xue & R.M.K. Saunders</i>	Tree	Cultivated
5	Menispermaceae	<i>Tinospora cordifolia (Willd.) Hook. f. & Thomson</i>	Climber	Wild
6	Nymphaeaceae	<i>Nymphaea nouchali Burm. f.</i>	Herb	Wild
7		<i>Nymphaea stellata Willd.</i>	Herb	Wild
8	Papaveraceae	<i>Fumaria indica (Hausskn.) Pugsley</i>	Herb	Wild
9		<i>Argemone mexicana L.</i>	Herb	Wild
10	Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica cretica subsp. cretica</i>	Herb	Cultivated
11		<i>Brassica oleracea L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
12		<i>Brassica napus L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
13		<i>Brassica juncea (L.) Czern.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
14		<i>Brassica rapa L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
15		<i>Lepidium didymium L.</i>	Herb	Wild
16		<i>Eruca vesicaria (L.) Cav.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
17		<i>Raphanus raphanistrum L.</i>	Herb	Wild
18		<i>Rorippa indica (L.) Hiern</i>	Herb	Wild
19		<i>Sisymbrium irio L.</i>	Herb	Wild
20	Capparidaceae	<i>Cleome viscosa L.</i>	Herb	Wild
21		<i>Capparis decidua (Forssk.) Edgew.</i>	Tree	Wild
22		<i>Capparis sepiaria L.</i>	Shrub/Tree	Wild
23		<i>Crataeva religiosa Hook.f. & Thoms.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
24	Caryophyllaceae	<i>Stellaria media (L.) Vill.</i>	Herb	Wild
25		<i>Spergula arvensis L.</i>	Herb	Wild
26		<i>Silene conoidea L.</i>	Herb	Wild
27	Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca grandiflora Hook.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
28		<i>Portulaca pilosa L.</i>	Herb	Wild

29	Tamaricaceae	<i>Tamarix dioica</i> Roxb.	Shrub	Wild
30	Bombacaceae	<i>Bombax ceiba</i> L.	Tree	Cultivated
31	Malvaceae	<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i> (L.) Moench	Herb	Cultivated
32		<i>Abelmoschus ficulneus</i> (L.) Wight & Arn.	Herb	Wild
33		<i>Abelmoschus manihot</i> (L.) Medik.	Shrub	Cultivated
34		<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.) Sweet	Shrub	Wild
35		<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> L.	Shrub	Cultivated
36		<i>Malva pusilla</i> Sm.	Herb	Wild
37		<i>Malvastrum coromandelianum</i> (L.) Garcke	Shrub	Wild
38		<i>Sida acuta</i> Burm.f.	Herb	Wild
39		<i>Sida cordifolia</i> L.	Shrub	Wild
40		<i>Sida rhombifolia</i> L.	Herb	Wild
41		<i>Urena lobata</i> L.	Shrub	Wild
42		<i>Pterospermum acerifolium</i> (L.) Willd.	Tree	Cultivated
43		<i>Triumfetta pentandra</i> A.Rich.	Herb	Wild
44		Zygophyllaceae	<i>Kallstroemia maxima</i> (L.) Hook. & Arn.	Herb
45	Oxalidaceae	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	Herb	Wild
46	Rutaceae	<i>Citrus aurantiifolia</i> (Christm.) Swingle	Shrub	Cultivated
47		<i>Citrus glauca</i> (Lindl.) Burkill	Tree	Cultivated
48		<i>Citrus reticulata</i> L.	Shrub	Cultivated
49		<i>Citrus sinensis</i> (L.) Osbeck.	Shrub	Cultivated
50		<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corrêa	Tree	Cultivated
51		<i>Bergera koenigii</i> L.	Shrub	Wild
52	Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss.	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
53		<i>Melia azedarach</i> L.	Tree	Cultivated
54		<i>Chukrasia tabularis</i> A. Juss.	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
55		<i>Toona ciliata</i> M.Roem.	Tree	Wild
56	Rhamnaceae	<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i> Mill.	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
57		<i>Ziziphus nummularia</i> (Burm. f.) Wt. & Arn.	S	Wild
58	Vitaceae	<i>Causonis trifolia</i> (L.) Mabb. & J. Wen.	Climber	Wild
59		<i>Vitis vinifera</i> L.	Climber	Cultivated
60	Sapindaceae	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	Climber	Wild
61		<i>Sapindus saponaria</i> L.	Tree	Cultivated
62		<i>Litchi chinensis</i> Sonn.	Tree	Cultivated
63	Burseraceae	<i>Commiphora wightii</i> (Arn.) Bhandari	Tree	Wild
64	Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
65	Moringaceae	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	Tree	Cultivated
66	Fabaceae	<i>Vicia sativa</i> L.	Climber	Wild
67		<i>Vicia hirsuta</i> (L.) Gray	Climber	Wild
68		<i>Melilotus indicus</i> (L.) All.	Herb	Wild
69		<i>Lablab purpureus</i> (L.) Sweet	Climber	Cultivated
70		<i>Lathyrus aphaca</i> L.	Herb	Wild
71		<i>Lathyrus oleraceus</i> Lam.	Herb	Cultivated
72		<i>Lathyrus vestitus</i> Nutt.	Herb	Cultivated
73		<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i> Roxb. ex DC.	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
74		<i>Dalbergia paniculata</i> (Roxb.) Thoth	Tree	Wild/Cultivated
75		<i>Crotalaria medicaginea</i> var. <i>luxurians</i> (Benth)	Herb	Wild

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76		<i>Crotalaria medicaginea</i> Lam.	Herb	Wild
77		<i>Crotalaria spectabilis</i> Roth.	Herb	Cultivated
78		<i>Medicago polymorpha</i> L.	Herb	Wild
79		<i>Medicago sativa</i> L.	Herb	Wild
80		<i>Trifolium alexandrinum</i> L.	Herb	Cultivated
81		<i>Trifolium fragiferum</i> L.	Herb	Wild
82		<i>Trifolium resupinatum</i> L.	Herb	Cultivated
83		<i>Trigonella balansae</i> Boiss. & Reut.	Herb	Cultivated
84		<i>Trigonella foenum-graecum</i> L.	Herb	Cultivated
85		<i>Vigna mungo</i> (L.) Hepper	Herb	Cultivated
86		<i>Vigna radiata</i> (L.) R. Wilczek	Herb	Cultivated
87		<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> (L.) Walp.	Herb	Cultivated
88		<i>Teramnus labialis</i> (L.f.) Spreng.	Climber	Wild
89		<i>Cyamopsis tetragonoloba</i> (L.) Taub.	Herb	Cultivated
90		<i>Aeschynomene indica</i> L.	Herb	Wild
91		<i>Indigofera tsiangiana</i> Metcalf	Herb	Wild
92		<i>Erythrina variegata</i> L.	Tree	Cultivated
93		<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Kuntze	Tree	Cultivated
94		<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
95		<i>Vicia lens</i> (L.) Coss. & Germ.	Herb	Cultivated
96		<i>Piliostigma malabaricum</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
97		<i>Bauhinia variegata</i> L.	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
98		<i>Grona heterophylla</i> (Willd.) H. Ohashi & K. Ohashi	Herb	Wild
99		<i>Delonix regia</i> (Bojer ex Hook.) Raf.	Tree	Cultivated
100		<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i> (Lam.) de Wit.	Tree	Wild
101	Caesalpinaceae	<i>Guilandina bonduc</i> L.	Tree	Cultivated
102		<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Tree	Cultivated
103		<i>Senna sulfurea</i> (DC. ex Collad.) H.S. Irwin & Barneby	Tree	Cultivated
104	Mimosaceae	<i>Albizia lebbek</i> (L.) Benth.	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
105		<i>Albizia procera</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	Tree	Wild
106		<i>Prosopis cineraria</i> (L.) Druce	Tree	Wild
107		<i>Neltuma juliflora</i> (Sw.) Raf.	Tree	Wild
108		<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> A. Cunn. Benth.	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
109		<i>Senegalia catechu</i> (L.f.) P.J.H. Hurter & Mabb.	Tree	Wild
110		<i>Senegalia modesta</i> (Wall.) P.J.H. Hurter	Tree	Wild
111		<i>Vachellia nilotica</i> (L.) P.J.H. Hurter & Mabb.	Tree	Wild
112	Rosaceae	<i>Eriobotrya japonica</i> (Thunb.) Lindl.	Tree	Cultivated
113		<i>Pyrus pyrifolia</i> (Burm. f.) Nakai	Tree	Cultivated
114		<i>Prunus amygdalus</i> Batsch	Tree	Cultivated
115		<i>Rosa x alba</i> L.	Shrub	Cultivated
116		<i>Rosa indica</i> L.	Shrub	Cultivated
117		<i>Malus domestica</i> (Suckow) Borkh.	Tree	Cultivated
118	Crassulaceae	<i>Kalanchoe pinnata</i> (Lam.) Pers.	Herb	Cultivated
119	Combretaceae	<i>Combretum indicum</i> (L.) De Filippis	Climber	Cultivated
120		<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wight &	Tree	Cultivated

		Arn.		
121		<i>Terminalia bellirica (Gaertn.) Roxb.</i>	Tree	Wild
122		<i>Terminalia chebula Retz.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
123	Myrtaceae	<i>Melaleuca citina (Curtis) Dum. Cours.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
124		<i>Melaleuca viminalis (Sol. ex Gaertn.) Byrnes</i>	Tree	Cultivated
125		<i>Eucalyptus globulus Labill.</i>	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
126		<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis Sm.</i>	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
127		<i>Psidium guajava L.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
128		<i>Syzygium cumini (L.) Skeels</i>	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
129		Lythraceae	<i>Lagerstroemia indica L.</i>	Tree
130	<i>Lagerstroemia speciosa (L.) Pers.</i>		Tree	Cultivated
131	<i>Lawsonia inermis L.</i>		Shrub	Wild/ Cultivated
132	<i>Trapa natans L.</i>		Herb	Wild
133	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Coccinia grandis (L.) Voigt</i>	Climber	Wild
134		<i>Trichosanthes cucumerina L.</i>	Herb	Wild
135		<i>Luffa acutangula (L.) Roxb.</i>	Climber	Cultivated
136		<i>Luffa cylindrica (L.) Rox.</i>	Climber	Cultivated
137		<i>Mukia maderaspatana (L.) Cogn.</i>	Climber	Wild
138		<i>Momordica charantia L.</i>	Climber	Cultivated
139		<i>Citrullus colocynthis (L.) Schrad.</i>	Climber	Wild
140		<i>Benincasa fistulosa (Stocks) H. Schaef. & S.S. Renner</i>	Climber	Cultivated
141		<i>Citrullus lanatus (Thunb.) Matsum. & Nakai</i>	Climber	Cultivated
142		<i>Cucumis melo L.</i>	Climber	Wild/ Cultivated
143		<i>Cucumis sativus L.</i>	Climber	Cultivated
144		<i>Cucurbita maxima Duchesne</i>	Climber	Cultivated
145		<i>Cucurbita moschata Duchesne</i>	Climber	Cultivated
146		<i>Cucurbita pepo L.</i>	Climber	Cultivated
147		<i>Lagenaria siceraria (Molina) Standl.</i>	Climber	Cultivated
148	Caricaceae	<i>Carica papaya L.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
149	Punicaceae	<i>Punica granatum L.</i>	Shrub	Cultivated
150	Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia perennis L.</i>	Herb	Wild
151	Molluginaceae	<i>Hypertelis cerviana (L.) Thulin</i>	Herb	Wild
152	Apiaceae	<i>Centella asiatica (L.) Urb.</i>	Herb	Wild
153		<i>Coriandrum sativum L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
154		<i>Daucus carota L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
155		<i>Foeniculum vulgare Mill.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
156		<i>Pimpinella major (L.) Huds</i>	Herb	Wild
157		<i>Trachyspermum ammi (L.) Sprague</i>	Herb	Cultivated
158	Rubiaceae	<i>Neolamarckia cadamba (Roxb.) Bosser</i>	Tree	Wild/ Cultivated
159 C		<i>Galium aparine L.</i>	Herb	Wild

160		<i>Launaea procumbens</i> (Roxb.) Ramayya & Rajagopal	Herb	Wild
161		<i>Sonchus arvensis</i> L.	Herb	Wild
162		<i>Sonchus wightianus</i> DC.	Herb	Wild
163		<i>Cyanthillium cinereum</i> (L.) H. Rob.	Herb	Wild
164		<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L.	Herb	Wild
165		<i>Erigeron sublyratus</i> Roxb. ex DC.	Herb	Wild
166		<i>Erigeron bonariensis</i> L.	Herb	Wild
167		<i>Erigeron canadensis</i> L.	Herb	Wild
168		<i>Caesulia axillaris</i> Roxb.	Herb	Wild
169		<i>Anaphalis subdecurrens</i> (DC.) Gamble	Herb	Wild
170	Asteraceae	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	Shrub	Wild
171		<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Herb	Wild
172		<i>Bidens pilosa</i> L.	Herb	Wild
173		<i>Tridax procumbens</i> (L.) L.	Herb	Wild
174		<i>Verbesina encelioides</i> (Cav.) Benth. & Hook.f. ex A. Gray	Herb	Wild
175		<i>Artemisia scoparia</i> Waldst. & Kit.	Herb	Wild
176		<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.	Herb	Wild
177		<i>Chrysanthemum indicum</i> L.	Herb	Cultivated
178		<i>Cirsium arvense</i> (L.) Scop.	Herb	Wild
179		<i>Dahlia pinnata</i> Cav.	Herb	Cultivated
180		<i>Helianthus annuus</i> L.	Shrub	Cultivated
181		<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.	Herb	Cultivated
182		<i>Lactuca dissecta</i> D. Don	Herb	Wild
183		<i>Tagetes erecta</i> L.	Herb	Cultivated
184	Sphenocleaceae	<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i> Gaetrn.	Herb	Wild
185	Plumbaginaceae	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> L.	Herb	Wild
186	Primulaceae	<i>Anagallis arvensis</i> L.	Herb	Wild
187	Sapotaceae	<i>Manilkara zapota</i> (L.) P. Royen	Tree	Cultivated
188		<i>Pouteria sapota</i> (Jacq.) H.E. Moore & Stearn	Tree	Cultivated
189	Oleaceae	<i>Jasminum grandiflorum</i> L.	Shrub	Cultivated
190		<i>Jasminum sambac</i> (L.) Sol.	Shrub	Cultivated
191		<i>Catharanthus roseus</i> (L.) G. Don	Herb	Cultivated
192		<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) R. Br.	Tree	Cultivated
193	Apocynaceae	<i>Carissa spinarum</i> L.	Shrub	Wild/ Cultivated
194		<i>Cascabela thevetia</i> (L.) Lippold	Shrub	Cultivated
195		<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	Tree	Cultivated
196		<i>Tabernaemontana divaricata</i> (L.) R. Br. ex Roem. & Schult.	Shrub	Cultivated
197	Asclepiadaceae	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) W.T. Aiton	Shrub	Wild
198		<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) W.T. Aiton	Shrub	Wild
199		<i>Oxystelma esculentum</i> (L. f.) Sm.	Shrub	Wild
200	Apocynaceae	<i>Pergularia daemia</i> (Sw.) Chiouv.	Climber	Wild
201	Gentianaceae	<i>Centaurium pulchellum</i> (Sw.) Hayek ex Hand.-Mazz., Stadlm., Janch. & Faltis	Herb	Wild
202	Boraginaceae	<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> G. Forst.	Tree	Wild
203		<i>Euploca strigosa</i> (Willd.) Diane & Hilger	Herb	Wild
204	Convolvulaceae	<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i> Roxb.	Climber	Wild
205		<i>Evolvulus nummularius</i> (L.) L.	Herb	Wild
206		<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i> Forssk.	Climber	Wild
207		<i>Ipomoea batatas</i> (L.) Lam	Climber	Wild
208		<i>Ipomoea carnea</i> subsp. <i>fistulosa</i> (Mart. ex	Climber	Wild

		<i>Choisy) D.F. Austin</i>	r	
209		<i>Ipomoea grandifolia (Dammer) O'Donell</i>	Climber	Wild
210		<i>Ipomoea nil (L.) Roth</i>	Climber	Wild
211		<i>Ipomoea pes-tigridis L.</i>	Climber	Wild
212		<i>Convolvulus arvensis L.</i>	Climber	Wild
213		<i>Convolvulus prostratus Forssk.</i>	Herb	Wild
214		<i>Merremia hederacea (Burm. f.) Hallier f.</i>	Climber	Wild
215		<i>Physalis angulata L.</i>	Herb	Wild
216		<i>Withania somnifera (L.) Dunal</i>	Herb	Wild/Cultivated
217		<i>Capsicum annuum L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
218		<i>Nicotiana plumbaginifolia Viv.</i>	Herb	Wild
219	Solanaceae	<i>Datura innoxia Mill</i>	Herb	Wild
220		<i>Datura metel L.</i>	Herb	Wild
221		<i>Solanum melongena L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
222		<i>Solanum americanum Mill.</i>	Herb	Wild
223		<i>Solanum tuberosum L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
224		<i>Solanum torvum Sw.</i>	Shrub	Wild
225		<i>Lycopersicon esculentum Mill.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
226		<i>Mazus pumilus (Burm. f.) Steenis</i>	Herb	Wild
227	Scrophulariaceae	<i>Bacopa monnieri (L.) Wettst.</i>	Herb	Wild
228		<i>Veronica arvensis L.</i>	Herb	Wild
229		<i>Veronica anagallis-aquatica L.</i>	Herb	Wild
230	Pedaliaceae	<i>Sesamum indicum L.</i>	Shrub	Wild/Cultivated
231		<i>Campsis radicans (L.) Bureau</i>	Shrub	Cultivated
232	Bignoniaceae	<i>Tecomella undulata (Sm.) Seem.</i>	Tree	Wild/Cultivated
233		<i>Tecoma stans (L.) Juss. ex Kunth</i>	Shrub	Cultivated
234		<i>Jacaranda mimosifolia D.Don</i>	Tree	Cultivated
235		<i>Dicliptera bupleuroides Nees</i>	Herb	Wild
236	Acanthaceae	<i>Eranthemum pulchellum Andrews</i>	Shrub	Wild
237		<i>Rungia pectinata (L.) Nees</i>	Herb	Wild
238		<i>Justicia adhatoda L.</i>	Shrub	Wild
239	Verbenaceae	<i>Lantana camara L.</i>	Shrub	Wild
240		<i>Duranta erecta L.</i>	Shrub	Cultivated
241		<i>Tectona grandis L. f.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
242		<i>Anisomeles indica (L.) Kuntze</i>	Herb	Wild
243	Lamiaceae	<i>Ocimum basilicum L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
244		<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
245		<i>Salvia plebeia R. Br.</i>	Herb	Wild
246	Plantaginaceae	<i>Antirrhinum majus L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
247		<i>Boerhavia diffusa L.</i>	Herb	Wild
248	Nyctaginaceae	<i>Bougainvillea glabra Choisy</i>	Climber	Wild
249		<i>Bougainvillea spectabilis Willd.</i>	Climber	Wild
250		<i>Mirabilis jalapa L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
251		<i>Alternanthera sessilis (L.) DC.</i>	Herb	Wild
252		<i>Gomphrena celosoides Mart.</i>	Herb	Wild
253	Amaranthaceae	<i>Pupalia lappacea (L.) Juss.</i>	Shrub	Wild
254		<i>Digera muricata (L.) Mart.</i>	Herb	Wild
255		<i>Celosia argentea L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
256		<i>Bassia indica (Wight) A.J. Scott</i>	Herb	Cultivated

257		<i>Achyranthes aspera L.</i>	Herb	Wild
258		<i>Amaranthus spinosus L.</i>	Herb	Wild
259		<i>Amaranthus viridis L.</i>	Herb	Wild
260		<i>Spinacia oleracea L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
261	Chenopodiaceae	<i>Chenopodium murale (L.) S. Fuentes, Uotila & Borsch</i>	Herb	Wild
262		<i>Chenopodium album L.</i>	Herb	Wild
263	Basellaceae	<i>Basella alba L.</i>	Climber	Wild
264	Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria barbata (L.) H. Hara</i>	Herb	Wild
265		<i>Polygonum plebeium R.Br.</i>	Herb	Wild
266		<i>Rumex dentatus L.</i>	Herb	Wild
267	Proteaceae	<i>Grevillea robusta A.Cunn. ex R.Br.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
268	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia helioscopia L.</i>	Herb	Wild
269		<i>Euphorbia hirta L.</i>	Herb	Wild
270		<i>Euphorbia neriiifolia L.</i>	Shrub	Wild
271		<i>Euphorbia royleana Boiss.</i>	Shrub	Cultivated
272		<i>Euphorbia thymifolia L.</i>	Herb	Wild
273		<i>Jatropha curcas L.</i>	Shrub	Wild
274		<i>Jatropha integerrima Jacq.</i>	Shrub	Wild
275		<i>Croton bonplandianus Baill.</i>	Herb	Wild
276		<i>Ricinus communis L.</i>	Tree	Wild
277		<i>Phyllanthus emblica L.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
278		<i>Phyllanthus reticulatus Poir.</i>	Shrub	Wild
279		<i>Phyllanthus niruri L.</i>	Herb	Wild
280		<i>Putranjiva roxburghii Wall.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
281	Casuarineae	<i>Casuarina equisetifolia L.</i>	Tree	Wild Cultivated /
282	Salicaceae	<i>Populus deltoides W. Bartram ex Marshall</i>	Tree	Wild Cultivated /
283	Ulmaceae	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia (Roxb.) Planch.</i>	Tree	Wild Cultivated /
284	Cannabaceae	<i>Cannabis sativa L.</i>	Herb	Wild
285	Moraceae	<i>Ficus benghalensis L.</i>	Tree	Wild Cultivated /
286		<i>Ficus carica L.</i>	Tree	Wild
287		<i>Ficus elastica Roxb. ex Hornem.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
288		<i>Ficus racemosa Roxb.</i>	Tree	Wild Cultivated /
289		<i>Ficus religiosa L.</i>	Tree	Wild Cultivated /
290		<i>Ficus lacor Buch.-Ham.</i>	Tree	Wild Cultivated /
291		<i>Ficus palmata Forsk.</i>	Shrub	Wild
292		<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus Lam.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
293		<i>Artocarpus lacucha Buch.-Ham.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
294		<i>Morus alba L.</i>	Tree	Wild
295	<i>Morus indica L.</i>	Tree	Wild	
296	Hydrocharitaceae	<i>Hydrilla verticillata (L. f.) Royle</i>	Herb	Wild
297		<i>Najas minor All.</i>	Herb	Wild
298		<i>Vallisneria spiralis L.</i>	Herb	Wild
299	Iridaceae	<i>Gladiolus dalenii Van Geel</i>	Herb	Cultivated
300	Musaceae	<i>Musa balbisiana Colla</i>	Tree	Cultivated
301		<i>Musa paradisiaca L.</i>	Tree	Cultivated
302	Zingiberaceae	<i>Curcuma longa L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
303		<i>Zingiber officinale Roscoe</i>	Herb	Cultivated
304	Amaryllidaceae	<i>Allium cepa L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated
305		<i>Allium sativum L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated

306	Xanthorrhoeaceae	<i>Aloe vera</i> (L.) Burm.f.	Herb	Cultivated
307	Asparagaceae	<i>Asparagus officinalis</i> L.	Herb	Wild
308	Pontederiaceae	<i>Pontederia crassipes</i> Mart.	Herb	Wild
309	Commelinaceae	<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	Herb	Wild
310		<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm.f.	Herb	Wild
311	Arecaceae	<i>Phoenix sylvestris</i> (L.) Roxb.	Tree	Wild
312		<i>Hyophorbe lagenicaulis</i> (L. H. Bailey) H.E.Moore	Tree	Cultivated
313		<i>Roystonea regia</i> (Kunth) O.F.Cook	Tree	Cultivated
314	Typhaceae	<i>Typha angustifolia</i> L.	Herb	Wild
315		<i>Typha domingensis</i> Pers.	Herb	Wild
316	Araceae	<i>Colocasia esculenta</i> (L.) Schott	Herb	Wild
317		<i>Spirodela polyrhiza</i> (L.) Schleid.	Herb	Wild
318	Lemnaceae	<i>Lemna minor</i> L.	Herb	Wild
319	Nelumbonaceae	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertn.	Herb	Wild
320	Potamogetonaceae	<i>Potamogeton natans</i> L.	Herb	Wild
321		<i>Potamogeton perfoliatus</i> L.	Herb	Wild
322	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus alatus</i> subsp. <i>albus</i> (Nees) Lye	Herb	Wild
323		<i>Cyperus compressus</i> L.	Herb	Wild
324		<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Herb	Wild
325		<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Herb	Wild
326		<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> (L.) Willd.	Herb	Wild
327		<i>Setaria pumila</i> (Poir.) Roem. & Schult.	Herb	Wild
328		<i>Setaria verticillata</i> (L.) P.Beauv.	Herb	Wild
329		<i>Bambusa bambos</i> (L.) Voss	Tree	Wild / Cultivated
330		<i>Phragmites karka</i> (Retz.) Trin. ex Steud.	Herb	Wild
331		<i>Desmostachya bipinnata</i> (L.) Stapf	Herb	Wild
332	Poaceae	<i>Dinebra panicea</i> (Retz.) P.M. Peterson & N. Snow	Herb	Wild
333		<i>Arundo donax</i> L.	Herb	Wild
334		<i>Avena sativa</i> L.	Herb	Wild
335		<i>Cenchrus ciliaris</i> L.	Herb	Wild
336		<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Herb	Wild
337		<i>Dichanthium annulatum</i> (Forssk.) Stapf	Herb	Wild
338		<i>Digitaria longiflora</i> (Retz.) Pers.	Herb	Wild
339		<i>Ischaemum sayajiraoi</i> Raole & R.J. Desai	Herb	Wild
340		<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) P.Beauv.	Herb	Wild
341		<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Herb	Wild
342		<i>Enneapogon avenaceus</i> (Lindl.) C.E.Hubb.	Herb	Wild
343		<i>Eragrostis pilosa</i> (L.) P.Beauv.	Herb	Wild
344		<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> (L.) P.Beauv. ex Roem. & Schult.	Herb	Wild
345		<i>Hordeum vulgare</i> L.	Herb	Cultivated
346		<i>Oplismenus burmannii</i> (Retz.) P. Beauv	Herb	Wild
347		<i>Panicum maximum</i> Jacq.	Herb	Wild
348		<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	Herb	Wild
349		<i>Pennisetum typhoides</i> Rich.	Herb	Wild
350	<i>Pennisetum glaucum</i> (L.) R. Br.	Herb	Cultivated	
351	<i>Phalaris minor</i> Retz.	Herb	Wild	
352	<i>Poa annua</i> L.	Herb	Wild	
353	<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L.	Herb	Cultivated	
354	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	Herb	Cultivated	
355	<i>Polypogon monspeliensis</i> (L.) Desf.	Herb	Wild	
356	<i>Saccharum bengalense</i> Retz.	Herb	Wild	
357	<i>Saccharum officinarum</i> L.	Herb	Cultivated	
358		<i>Saccharum spontaneum</i> L.	Herb	Wild

359		<i>Tripidium ravennae (L.) H. Scholz</i>	Herb	Wild
360		<i>Sorghum halepense (L.) Pers.</i>	Herb	Wild
361		<i>Chrysopogon zizanioides (L.) Roberty</i>	Herb	Wild
362		<i>Zea mays L.</i>	Herb	Cultivated

Conclusion: District Patiala is rich in floral diversity. Proper updating these records is an essential component so that needful strategies should be planned because Royals of Patiala created many jungles for the hunting purpose and they are still intact and further need to protect to conserve the biodiversity. Interacting with the people showed that they are willing to conserve biodiversity but lack of education, employment and awareness is the major reason for the overexploitation of the resources. So, Government and stakeholders should design such programs where locals can be promoted for their maximum involvement and participation for the conservation of national resources.

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